

But an increase in the "chemical adsorption" produced by the addition of non-electrolytes cannot be due to an increase in the charge on the particles on account of the adsorption of the similarly charged ions by them, because here no electrolyte is added. An actual increase in the value of the charge can take place by an increase in the dielectric constant or a decrease in the thickness of the double layer, according to the equation $e = VD/4\pi r^2$ provided the radius of the particle and the potential of the double layer remains the same. We agree with Mukherjee and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 704) that the potential of the double layer is not determined by the change in the dielectric constant, as Freundlich had assumed, and further it appears to us that the change in the value of the charge e , cannot be wholly explained by the change in the dielectric constant alone. It is rather more probable that the thickness of the double layer alters.

In this connection it is of importance to note that Wo. Ostwald (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, 42, 981) has pointed out that the "density of the charge instead of the magnitude of the charge" and the "compression of the double layer" might be responsible for the coagulation of a colloid; but certainly they are insufficient by themselves. Whether really an alteration in the thickness of the double layer is finally the cause of this increase in the concentration of the precipitating ion when the stabilisation is brought about by the addition of the non-electrolytes, further experiments can show. For the present it can only be taken as a suggestion.

Received August 11, 1939,

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

PYRIDINE COMPLEX OF METALLIC PERCHLORATES. PART I.

By P. C. SINHA AND R. C. RAY

Pyridine compounds of the perchlorates of silver, copper (ic), magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, cadmium, zinc, mercury(ic), manganese, nickel and cobalt have been prepared. Compositions and characteristics of these compounds have been described. It has been found that the same pyridine compound is formed whether anhydrous or hydrated perchlorates are employed. No relationship seems to exist between the size of the metal atom or its ion and the number of pyridine molecules it can co-ordinate.

A large number of complex compounds of pyridine with various inorganic salts have been described in literature.* Most of the earlier investigations were,

* Jørgensen (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1884, ii, 33, 502). Veret (*compt. rend.*, 1892, 115, 464; 1897, 124, 1155). Klobb, *ibid.*, 1894, 118, 1271; Reitzenstein, *Annalen*, 1874, 282, 267; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 19, 253. Pesci (*Gazzetta*, 1895, 25, 432). Pincoushn (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1897, 14, 385). Tombeck, (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1900, 21, 433; 1901, 22, 113). Litterscheid, (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1901, 239, 336; 1902, 240, 74). Grossmann (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 839), Pfeiffer and Pimmer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 48, 98). Werner *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1908, 39, 1538). Davis and Logan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2497). Werner, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2577). Zvyagintsev, *et al.* (*Dokl. akad. sci., U.S.S.R.*, 1937, No. 3, p. 1255).

however, concerned with the preparation and analytical compositions of the substances formed, and little attempts were made to determine the structure of the complex compounds. Davis and his co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1930, 52, 4069; 1934, 56, 1061; 1936, 58, 2153; 1940, 62, 1276) were the first to make a systematic study of the metal-pyridine compounds. They found that these compounds were true co-ordination complexes and showed that where the number of molecules of pyridine was greater than the co-ordination number of the metal, the extra pyridine molecules were merely adsorbed. They also determined the affinities with which C_5H_5N molecules were linked in the compound from measurements of their dissociation pressures at different temperatures.

An examination of the previous work of the metal-pyridine compounds indicates clearly the necessity of a thorough investigation of this class of compounds, mainly because of the divergent results obtained by different workers in the field. The present work has been therefore undertaken in order to inquire into the nature, conditions of formation, stability and other characteristics of these compounds and to investigate them from chemical as well as physical aspects. For this purpose it seemed desirable to make a systematic study of the complexes which formed with different metallic salts of the same acid, and salts of perchloric acid was selected chiefly for two reasons. In the first place, pyridine compounds of metal perchlorates are not known, and secondly, the amines of perchlorates of copper, silver, zinc, cadmium, calcium, strontium, barium, nickel and cobalt have been fully investigated by Ephraim and his collaborators (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 3103; 1915, 48, 638, 1770; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 296) and the amines of the perchlorates of the alkali and alkaline earth metals by Smeets (*Natur. Tijdschr.*, 1935, 17, 83, 213; 1939, 21, 149). As pyridine would replace ammonia, molecule for molecule, naturally parallelism between the ammonia-metal perchlorates and the pyridine compounds of the latter could be expected.

EXPERIMENTAL

Perchlorates of Ag, Cu^{II} , Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Cd, Zn, Hg (ic), Mn (ous) Ni and Co were prepared by the action of 20g. of perchloric acid (A.R.) on freshly precipitated and carefully washed oxide or carbonate of the respective metal. The resulting solutions were filtered where necessary and the filtrate, on concentration, gave crystals of the perchlorates which were separated from the liquid by filtering through a Buchner funnel and washed with ice-cold water. The crystals were dissolved in a small quantity of distilled water and recrystallised. The purity of the product was confirmed by analysis. All the perchlorates except that of silver contained water of crystallisation, and their composition agreed with those stated by earlier workers (Serullas, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1831, ii, 46 297; Salvadori, *Gasetta*, 1912, 42, 458; Weinland and Engraber, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1914, 84, 370; Willard and Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 286).

To prepare the pyridine compounds, 2 to 4 g. of the crystalline perchlorate were dissolved in 20 to 30 c.c. of specially purified and freshly distilled pyridine (b.p. 114.5°), the solution being effected by warming. The solution was then heated on a water-bath for a short time, and on cooling, beautiful crystals separated in every case. These were collected in a Gooch crucible, washed with a little cold pyridine, and

freed from the latter by suction. The crystals were dried by pressing between folds of filter paper and transferred into a glass-stoppered weighing bottle for analysis.

For determination of pyridine in the case of the colourless compounds, a small quantity of the substance was directly weighed out into an Erlenmeyer flask, dissolved in a little water and titrated with *N*/10-hydrochloric acid solution, using methyl orange as indicator. For estimation of pyridine in the coloured compound, a modification of the method described by Lange (*Ber.*, 1883, 21, 579) was followed. From the aqueous solution of a weighed quantity of the coloured compound, made strongly alkaline with sodium hydroxide, the pyridine was steam-distilled into standard *N*-sulphuric acid solution, and the excess of acid was then titrated back with *N*/2-sodium hydroxide solution. Blank experiments with weighed amounts of purified pyridine showed that the method is accurate to about 1% only, mainly on account of the fact that a sharp end-point is not obtained. Other indicators, such as methyl red, congo red, etc., were tried, but methyl orange gave the best results.

For determination of the metals, the solutions left after titration of pyridine in the case of the colourless compounds or those left in the round-bottomed flask after steam distillation in the case of the coloured compounds, were used. In many cases, estimation of the metals was also made directly with weighed quantities of pyridine compound, and the values obtained agreed well with those given after the removal of pyridine except in the cases of copper and cobalt where it was found that the presence of pyridine prevented complete deposition of the metals. Pyridine must also be previously removed for direct conversion of the pyridine compounds into sulphates by heating with concentrated sulphuric acid, otherwise decomposition takes place with explosion.

The composition of the compounds obtained with a short description of their properties and the analytical results are given below.

Compounds.	Properties.	Results of analysis.			
		Calc.		Found.	
		Metal.	Pyridine.	Metal.	Pyridine.
$\text{AgClO}_4 \cdot 4\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Colourless cubic crystals. Fairly stable.	20.59%	60.41%	20.1 ; 20.5%	60.1 ; 59.9%
$\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Small violet-blue crystals. Stable. Not hygroscopic.	10.98	54.66	10.8 ; 10.9	54.9 ; 55.5
$\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Colourless crystals. Extremely hygroscopic.	3.49	68.01	3.4 ; 3.3	67.6 ; 67.4
$\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Colourless crystals. Highly deliquescent in moist air. Unstable.	5.63	67.91	5.5 ; 5.4	66.0 ; 67.2
$\text{Sr}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Ditto.	11.52	62.35	11.4 ; 11.3	62.7 ; 62.2
$\text{Ba}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Colourless crystals. Deliquescent, but less so and more stable than Ca and Sr compounds.	16.96	58.54	17.5 ; 17.3	57.5 ; 58.1
$\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Colourless hexagonal pyramids. Fairly stable. Not hygroscopic.	11.27	54.46	11.2 ; 11.3	54.4 ; 54.8
$\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Stable colourless crystals. Not deliquescent.	14.30	60.39	14.6 ; 14.2	59.9 ; 59.2
$\text{Hg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Colourless crystals. Not hygroscopic. Quite stable.	22.95	54.29	22.9 ; 22.6	54.5 ; 53.7
$\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Lilac crystals. Not deliquescent. Partially hydrolysed with water.	6.20	71.36	6.0 ; 6.1	71.5 ; 71.6
$\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Pale green crystals. Stable. Not very hygroscopic.	8.04	64.32	8.3 ; 8.2	64.6 ; 64.7
$\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	Pink hexagonal prisms. Soluble in chloroform. Fairly stable.	8.05	64.81	8.1 ; 8.2	64.7 ; 64.9

It will be seen that the compounds of the alkaline earth metals and that of magnesium are extremely hygroscopic. They deliquesce so rapidly in moist air that it is almost impossible to separate them from pyridine during rainy season. When kept in a desiccator over sulphuric acid, all these pyridine compounds lose pyridine more or less rapidly. They, however take up pyridine when exposed to pyridine vapour and return to their original composition. It seems that these pyridine complexes are not interstitial compounds, because the crystalline form of the pyridine complex as well as its solubility in pyridine differs entirely from the corresponding perchlorate. The hydrated perchlorates generally form needle-like crystals, while the pyridine compounds assume various crystalline forms. For example, while AgClO_4 crystallises as long needles, $\text{AgClO}_4 \cdot 4\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ crystallises in the form of cubes, and while $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ comes out as hexagonal prisms, $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ forms needle-shaped crystals. The solubility of the perchlorate and its corresponding pyridine compound in water is also different.

It has been found that the water of crystallisation of the perchlorates has no influence on the formation of the pyridine compound. About 6 g. of needle-like crystals of hydrated magnesium perchlorate were heated first at 120° when about 30% of the water of crystallisation were lost, and then the temperature was gradually raised to $230\text{--}250^\circ$ until there was no further loss of water. The total loss of water amounted to 32.67%, while the theoretical value for the hexahydrate is 32.62%. The white anhydrous material thus obtained was taken out of the crucible while still hot, ground to powder and kept in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. The pyridine compound obtained by dissolving this anhydrous magnesium perchlorate had the same crystalline form and the same analytical composition as that given by $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Similarly when some crystals of barium perchlorate were heated to constant weight at 250° , they lost all water. The total loss of water amounted to 13.79% while the calculated value for $\text{Ba}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 13.85%. The anhydrous barium perchlorate also gave the same pyridine compound as the hydrated crystals.

DISCUSSION

As all these pyridine compounds separated from pyridine solutions, they must represent the highest possible pyridinated complexes. It will be seen from the table that the perchlorates of silver, copper and zinc can take up only 4 molecules of pyridine each, the perchlorates of magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, cadmium, mercury, nickel and cobalt 6 molecules of pyridine each, and manganese as many as 8 molecules of pyridine. In discussing the ammoniated compounds of metallic perchlorates, Ephraim (*Ner*, 1912, 45, 1323) stated that those metals whose atomic volume is less than 14 can take up 6 molecules of ammonia, but those metals whose atomic volumes are greater than this number cannot form stable hexammines. Those in which the atomic volumes are very large (Ba, Sr, Ca) give amines of a different class; these decompose readily with liberation of much ammonia and with no pause at the hexamine stage. As both ammonia and pyridine are co-ordinated to the metal atom through the nitrogen atom, it was expected that pyridine compounds would behave in the same manner as the ammonia compounds. From an examination of the pyridine

compounds described in the present paper, there appears to be no relationship between the number of molecules of pyridine which can be co-ordinated and the size of the metal atom or its ion. For instance, although copper and manganese have almost the same atomic volumes, only 4 molecules of pyridine can attach themselves to copper, but manganese can take up double this number. In fact, similar anomalous behaviour is also observed when the amines of metallic perchlorates are compared. When the ammoniated compounds of the perchlorates are examined, it is found that the highest ammine of zinc has the formula $Zn(ClO_4)_2 \cdot 6NH_3$ (Ephraim, and Zapata, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 296) and that of silver has the formula $AgClO_4 \cdot 3NH_3$, although the sizes of the metal atoms or their ions do not justify that the former should take up twice the number of NH_3 molecules as the latter. It appears therefore that the co-ordination number does not depend merely on the size of the co-ordinating metal atom or its ion but rather on the capacity of expansion of its electronic orbits so that it may be possible to accommodate all the electrons necessary to form the co-ordinate links. In recent years a considerable amount of research has centred round the determination of the structure of co-ordination compounds with all the powerful physical methods at the disposal of the modern chemist and old observations furnished in the light of the present-day knowledge, but it has not yet been possible to discover the factors which determine the co-ordination number of elements. There is increasing evidence in favour of the view that co-ordinate links and principal valencies are closely connected, and it seems, that it is necessary to determine the structure of co-ordination compounds as a whole and not of the central metal atom only.

Measurements of lowering of the freezing point and elevation of the boiling point, conductivity and dissociation pressures are in progress.

Received November 9, 1942.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE,
PATNA.
